

**Multi spiral Computed Tomography Analysis of Chronic Lung Disease
Complications in Patients Who Have Undergone Covid-19 Pneumonia**

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During the pandemic of a new coronavirus infection, the question of the possible consequences of the infection, the assessment of post-inflammatory changes and quality of life is widely discussed in clinical practice. As of November 14, 2021, according to the World Health Organization website, 254 million cases of the new coronavirus infection COVID-19 were registered, of which 5.1 million were fatal, 229.1 million patients recovered. Among the complications of infection caused by SARS-CoV-2, complications associated with damage to the lungs, heart and blood vessels, kidneys and central nervous system are distinguished [1, 2]. Among domestic and foreign publications, there are isolated works devoted to the long-term results of COVID-19 treatment [3].

The purpose of the study. To evaluate the features of the course of the inflammatory process, to study the condition of the lung tissue according to the results of multisection computed tomography (MSCT) 1, 3 and 6

months after completion of treatment in patients with COVID-19-associated

pneumonia.

Material and methods. The Main Military Clinical Hospital of the National Guard Troops of the Russian Federation analyzed the results of examination and treatment of 60 patients (41 (68%) men and 19 (32%) women) aged 37 to 81 years (average age – 52.5 ± 5.1 years) who were treated in the period from March 2020 to March 2021 about viral pneumonia caused by COVID-

19. The data obtained using classical radiography, MSCT of patients with varying degrees of severity of lung tissue damage, at admission, after 1, 3 and 6 months were analyzed. Depending on the degree of lung tissue damage, the patients were divided into four groups of 15 people each: with minimal damage according to computed tomography (CT-1), with mild damage (CT-2), moderate (CT- 3) and severe damage (CT-4). The criteria for inclusion in the study were the presence of clinical signs of COVID-19 viral pneumonia, the identification of changes in the lungs

characteristic of this disease using radiation diagnostics methods and positive results of reverse transcription polymerase chain reaction on SARSCoV-2. The exclusion criteria were the presence of bacterial pneumonia and other acute diseases of the upper respiratory tract. The main method of assessing the state of the pulmonary parenchyma after a new coronavirus infection was multi-slice computed tomography (MSCT) performed on a 16-slice computed tomograph Toshiba Aquilion (Japan); 128-slice computed tomograph Philips (Netherlands); 64-slice computed tomograph Siemens Go Top (Germany).

The severity of pneumonia was assessed on the basis of criteria approved by the order of the Moscow Department of Health of 08.04.2020 No. 373 and the order of 16.04.2020 No. 10-18-231/20. The degree of damage to the lung tissue was assessed by the volume of involvement of its parenchyma: does not correspond to pneumonia – CT-0, minimal – CT- 1 (less than 25%), mild – CT-2 (25-50%), moderate – CT-3 (50-75%) or severe – CT-4 (75- 100%) [1]. Laboratory diagnostics of COVID-19

was carried out by reverse transcription polymerase chain reaction. The material from the patient's oropharynx was examined. The study was conducted in the laboratories of Rospotrebnadzor and the Main Center for State Sanitary and Epidemiological Surveillance of the National Guard Troops of the Russian Federation. Statistical processing of the obtained results was carried out using the Microsoft Office 2016 software package.

References

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